

Sustainable Blue
Economy Partnership

Guidelines/Tutorials on how to best streamline
funds at national/regional/European level and use
other types of resources

Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

Synergies in the context of Horizon Europe and other funds are a way to amplify the impact of investments in research and innovation. One of the goals of the Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership (SBEP), a Member States / European Commission co-funded initiative to support the transition towards a climate neutral blue economy, is to facilitate its consortium members in benefiting from different financial resources in a synergetic manner, enabling the co-funding of research projects. This includes fostering collaboration to access various funding opportunities at both European Union (EU) and national/regional levels. To this end, a dedicated task was foreseen in the framework of the Partnership's activities.

Given the distinct governance structures of EU funding programmes at both EU and national/regional levels, achieving funding synergy can be challenging. However, by collaboratively developing strategic objectives with regional authorities and sharing lessons learned and experiences, Horizon Europe and other funding sources can be leveraged to co-finance successful projects, including within European Partnerships. To address this issue, this deliverable provides models and guidelines on such co-funding schemes that are subject to the management structures of each member state. We aim to provide recommendations that can be applied across Europe to optimise research funding, especially within the thematic intervention areas outlined by the Partnership. The outcomes of this deliverable leverage from a collaborative learning process among member states and entities, an invaluable process in facilitating the realization of these funding synergies, allowing for mutual exchange and sharing of lessons learned.

This deliverable builds up upon the outcomes of Deliverable 8.1 – Desk analysis on Common Provision Regulations and way to use European, regional and national funding streams, including for RPOs – which synthesizes and integrates raw data such as legislative documents, programme information, and guidelines regarding funding opportunities, in order to identify novelties and feasible ways for coherently streamline resources to enable the participation of other organizations, including Research Performing Organisations (RPOs). As

a step further, this deliverable reports targeted support actions to streamline the implementation of these synergies in the context of research and innovation projects relevant to the Partnership's objectives. Given several details in the regulations and practical issues to implement these synergies, we aim to provide users with insights into the potential suitability of these experiences across various countries.

2.0 METHODS

2.1 The role of the Partnership in streamlining funds and resources

The publication of guidelines by the European Commission aimed at fostering synergies between ERDF programmes and Horizon Europe (HE)¹² represents a significant milestone in facilitating, particularly from the Commissions perspective, the implementation of such synergies. The Partnership acknowledged this importance during the proposal preparation phase, leading to the dedication of an entire Work Package (WP8 – Additional Contributions to SBEP) to addressing and transferring methods for streamlining funds and supporting the implementation of linked activities, beyond competitive calls. The Partnership also acknowledges the considerable challenges associated with enabling these synergies, which largely hinge on the varying contexts and capabilities of individual countries and national/regional administrations.

The European Partnerships³ with Member States participation play a vital role in strengthening the European research landscape. They foster cross-border collaboration, align

¹ Commission Notice between Horizon Europe and ERDF programmes

https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=uriserv%3AOJ.C_.2022.421.01.0007.01.ENG&toc=OJ%3AC%3A2022%3A421%3AFULL / https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/information-sources/publications/communications/2022/synergies-between-erdf-programmes-and-horizon-europe_en

²The purpose of this document is to outline the new opportunities available to the managing authorities (MAs) of the cohesion policy programmes, national HE contact points and HE project promoters/proposers. The document is also intended to make it easier to use the relevant mechanisms (Seals of Excellence, transfers, cumulative funding (which can also be used to support Horizon Europe (HE) Co-funded and Institutionalised European Partnerships), support for Teaming, and upstream/downstream synergies).

³ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/european-partnerships-horizon-europe_en

research and innovation agendas, enhance skills, and boost the absorption capacity of European businesses, while further structuring the European Research Area. A central aim of these Partnerships is to achieve scientific, managerial, and financial integration of national research programmes in their respective domains.

The Partnerships, including SBEP, are key drivers for synergies between funding schemes, by bringing in and coordinating the use of resources available from EU and national instruments, programmes and funds. It is possible, for instance, to use European Structural and Investment Funds – ESIF (EAFRD, ESF, ERDF, ~~RRF~~, etc.) – ~~funds~~ in the context of co-funded Partnerships⁴. Furthermore, collaboration between a Partnership and potential alternative funding streams may also extend to engagement with the management authorities overseeing the ESIFs.

European Partnership: Union with private and/or public partners that jointly support the development and implementation of an R&I programme:

- Co-funded European Partnerships: Union provides co-funding to an R&I programme implemented by national entities. SBEP belongs to this category.
- Institutionalised European Partnerships (Articles 185/187 TFEU): Union provides co-funding to a joint programme implemented by structures created for that purpose.

Effectively coordinating diverse funding streams, whether from national or European sources, is crucial. Member States determine how to leverage multiple funding streams for co-financing research projects. However, a significant gap remains in consistently identifying the most suitable mechanisms for co-funding organizations in collaborative projects alongside other entities.

To maximize available funds and accelerate progress while preventing the isolation of results within specific communities (e.g., specific target groups of ESIFs), it is essential to enhance dialogue and cooperation among various stakeholders, including between the business and

⁴ <https://www.era-learn.eu/partnerships-in-a-nutshell/type-of-networks/co-funded-european-partnerships>

scientific sectors, as well as across member states and regions. Achieving this level of synergies involves several key actions. As such it is relevant to understand “who is doing what” across Europe, and this may be facilitated by identifying projects with similar objectives among European Missions, Partnerships, Structural Funds and other mechanisms. For instance, the Portfolio analysis of the EU mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030” (European Commission 2023)⁵, and the Horizon 2020-Interreg Synergies Mapping Tool⁶ (which combines thematic and regional information in order to identify potential synergies between these two funding streams), may provide valuable insights for the Partnership to learn from and implement synergies effectively in the future. In parallel, Deliverable 8.1 has provided a desk analysis on the use of European, regional and national funding streams, for different member states. On a further step, the Partnership focus has shifted towards the practical operationalization of these synergies, including through best practices’ sharing across countries. This involves implementing mechanisms to facilitate collaboration and leverage resources effectively across different funding streams. Thence, the Partnership is actively seeking pathways to facilitate funding synergies between EU funds and co-funded research and innovation programmes. We aim to explore possibilities to leverage other nationally available funding sources and resources than traditional. This includes the following key overarching actions:

1. **Optimal synergy of financial resources available for participants to (co)funded research projects**, specifically leveraging financial streams available in each member country, including EU Regional Development Fund (ERDF), Smart Specialization Strategies (see box below), Next Generation EU, and other relevant programmes.
2. **Guidelines and protocols for the involvement and utilization of in-kind resources**, i.e. deployed through contribution different from in cash, including the sharing of research infrastructures and capacity building activities, both within competitive calls and other activities in the partnership.

⁵ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/dfc5df4f-0073-11ee-87ec-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

⁶ https://dashboard.tech.ec.europa.eu/qs_digit_dashboard_mt/public/sense/app/77ebaa1f-43ff-4c4c-ab8f-a21b102259a0/sheet/371667d5-31a8-4cbb-b4ca-ece4bbcc02a8/state/analysis

3. **Implementing the in-kind participation to the partnership activity**, through a mapping/scouting process of available in-kind resources and research infrastructures, to drive the process of not implemented through competitive calls.

Actions 1 from the above list are the main focus of this deliverable, which is executed under Task 8.2 of the Partnership, whereas actions 2 and 3 are targeted primarily by other Tasks respectively, with some information provided also in this deliverable, including a summary in Section 4.0.

The Smart Specialization Strategy (S3) is adopted by EU Member States and regions to identify objectives, priorities, and actions aimed at optimizing the impact of investments in research and innovation. This strategic approach focuses resources on areas with the highest potential for growth, with the overarching aim of maximizing outcomes, enhancing competitiveness, and fostering the creation of high-quality employment.

2.2 Information provision and access

The Partnership implemented various enablers to enhance collaboration and resource consolidation on how to support Member States (MS) and Associated Countries (AC) to access funding streams synergistically. Primarily under WP8, the following actions have been undertaken by the Partnership:

- Analysis of several national and EU programmes that would be eligible for co-financing the institutions of the Partnership, improving synergies to reduce fragmentation and maximise the impact of research activities. This also included a desk analysis of the Common Provision Regulation (CPR).
- Dedicated events and sessions, either presential or online, including:
 - A Dedicated session on “Connectivity: Leveraging different funding streams” at the kick-off meeting of the Partnership (January 2023).
 - A Webinar on “How to provide synergy of funding in Horizon Europe: the case of the European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund (EMFAF)” (April 2023). This seminar delved into practical experiences and lessons learned

from successfully implementing synergies between EMFAF and Horizon Europe (HE) in Finland.

- A focus session on “Alignment of funding streams” at the 2nd meeting of the Partnership’s Steering Committee (May 2023). Countries shared successful stories in the framework of the Steering Committee, a guidance structure where MS with up to four representatives from different ministries sit together with the EC in order to give advice and information to the Partnership at strategic level.
- Presentation on “follow-up on synergies with other funding streams” at the 3rd meeting of the Steering Committee (October 2023).
- Focus session on ‘Widening: aligning structural funds: the case of Cyprus Research and Innovation Foundation and of Emilia-Romagna Region’ at the 4th meeting of the Steering Committee (February 2024).
- Widening roadmap leading to the engagement of one regional authority (Emilia Romagna Region from Italy) in the Partnership Consortium as a funding organization contributing through Structural Funds.
- Dedicated task on uptake of projects results (Task 7.4 of the Partnership).
- Direct contacts with partners and funding providers from various MS and AC, and the Commission (including e.g., DG MARE) to obtain specific information on available funding streams and their implementation.

These actions enabled a collaborative learning process among member states and entities, and we consolidated the outcomes of these various actions into guidelines detailed in the following sections. These contents include showcasing successful stories on creating funding synergies at national level and explanation of how these funding synergies are put in place from an operational point of view, leveraging support within the partnership’s knowledge-sharing framework. Challenges identified prompt a proposed roadmap for resolution. Our approach emphasizes lessons learned over best practices, owing to the novelty and evolving nature of such practices.

This dedicated support aimed at facilitating the seamless implementation of funding synergies for research and innovation (R&I) projects will continue beyond the completion of this deliverable. The task team will proceed to develop and refine models and guidelines to support the optimization of research funding. All pertinent information will be collated, standardized, and integrated into an easily accessible format, which will be disseminated to the consortium through an upcoming interactive digital report. Additionally, the task team will continue to organise capacity-building actions (such as workshops, and publication of tutorials and guidelines).

3.0 STREAMLINING FUNDING SYNERGIES BETWEEN EU FUNDS AND CO-FUNDED RESEARCH AND INNOVATION PROGRAMMES

TOP LINES

Synergies between Horizon Europe and Cohesion Policy programmes:

- Preconditions:
 - At programming level: alignment of strategies and co-creation:
 - HE strategic planning and Work Programmes.
 - ERDF, ESF+, EMFAF and other programmes.
 - At operational level: alignment of legal provisions in the frameworks:
 - Horizon Europe/Annex IV⁷.
 - Common Provisions Regulation (CPR)⁸.
 - EU State aid rules – the General Block Exemption Regulation ('GBER')⁹.
 - Joint support initiatives:
 - Seal of Excellence Community of Practice.

⁷ https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:8a5fc557-e743-11ec-a534-01aa75ed71a1.0001.02/DOC_3&format=PDF

⁸ https://commission.europa.eu/funding-tenders/find-funding/funding-management-mode/common-provisions-regulation_en

⁹ https://competition-policy.ec.europa.eu/state-aid/legislation/regulations_en

- Commission Notice – Guidance on Synergies (OJ C 421 of 4/11/2022)¹⁰.
- Types of synergies:
 - Seal of Excellence:
 - Pipeline of excellent R&I projects identified for funding.
 - Leveraging of HE mechanisms and visibility, and economic impact at regional level.
 - Transfers:
 - Strengthens participation in HE for MS with low success rates.
 - Preserves administrative capacity at national/regional level.
 - Cumulative funding: Allows pooling funding from two different instruments in one project (provision of no double funding still applies).
 - Synergies in European Partnerships.
 - Combined funding.
 - Upstream and downstream synergies.

Management of EU funds are regulated by the Common Provisions Regulation (CPR) and fund specific regulations. This regulatory framework establishes detailed rules for programming of the funds as well as management of the funds (application, evaluation, selection, decision making and payment processes), and reporting and control.

3.1 Smart Specialization Strategies (S3)

To effectively implement synergies, a strategic alignment of objectives of different programmes (Smart Specialisation Strategies – S3 – & Operational Programmes) may be required.

¹⁰ https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=uriserv%3AOJ.C_.2022.421.01.0007.01.ENG&toc=OJ%3AC%3A2022%3A421%3AFULL / https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/information-sources/publications/communications/2022/synergies-between-erdf-programmes-and-horizon-europe_en

Specifically, alignment of the Smart Specialisation Strategies (S3) is conditional to access to the synergy in the case of DG REGIO, but not for DG MARE. DG MARE is putting effort on mobilizing stakeholders towards the implementation of the Smart Specialisation Strategy for the Sustainable Blue Economy through cooperation. Given that both the Partnership and DG MARE have already identified innovative priority research areas, it is possible to find common areas of potential innovation for stakeholders to create interregional partnerships under the umbrella of the new platform of the Smart Specialisation for Blue Economy¹¹. Regarding EMFAF, their focus is on synergies among different funding schemes in order to provide opportunities to stakeholders to address a particular fund to implement their Smart Specialisation Strategies, and for cooperation. Also, in the case of Cohesion Policy¹² the entry point is the Smart Specialisation Strategy so the investments must meet the criteria that are set up therein.

3.2 Horizon Europe (HE)

TOP LINES

- Synergies with Horizon Europe are possible by:
 - A strategic approach (building on smart specialization strategy) and
 - A concrete combination of fundings (bringing together HE and other funds to the same project, including ERDF, ESF+, EMFAF and EAFRD)
- Managing authorities from MS may decide to directly provide support from ERDF, EMFAF, or other funds to operations selected under a programme co-funded by HE (such as the co-funded SBEP or other Institutionalised European Partnerships)

Horizon Europe offers opportunities for co-financing with ERDF, ESF+, EMFAF, and EAFRD, prompting a closer examination of these possibilities. Since managing authorities of Member

¹¹ https://competition-policy.ec.europa.eu/state-aid/legislation/regulations_en

¹² https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/policy/what/investment-policy_en

States oversee these programmes, it is essential to understand how to effectively implement them while adhering to relevant rules and regulations.

The Commission Notice on synergies between Horizon Europe and the European Regional Development Funds Programmes serves as a blueprint for aligning resources and objectives, underscoring the crucial role of European Partnerships in orchestrating resources across diverse EU and national programmes and funds. Additionally, we draw attention, in the following boxes, to specific provisions of Horizon Europe Regulation Article 15¹³ and in Cluster 6¹⁴ of the Horizon Europe Work Programme.

Horizon Europe Regulation Art. 15.2(3): “Financial contributions under programmes co-financed by the ERDF, the ESF+, the EMFAF and the EAFRD may be considered to be a contribution of the participating Member State to European Partnerships under points (b) and (c) of Article 10(1) of this Regulation, provided that the relevant provisions of the Common Provisions Regulation for 2021-2027 and the fund-specific regulations are complied with.”

Horizon Europe Work programme (2023-24) - Cluster 6: “Horizon Europe is the R&I support programme in a system of European and national funding programmes that shares policy objectives. Through the programme, special attention will be given to ensuring cooperation between universities, scientific communities and industry, including small and medium-sized enterprises, and people and their representatives. This is in order to bridge gaps between genders, territories, generations and regional cultures, in particular to support women innovators and care for the needs of young people in shaping Europe’s future. Calls could take the form of EU synergy calls, meaning that projects that have been awarded a grant under the call could also receive funding under other EU programmes, including relevant shared management funds. In this context, project proposers should consider and actively seek synergies with, and, where appropriate, possibilities for further funding from:

- other R&I-relevant EU, national or regional programmes (such as the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF);
- the European Social Fund Plus (ESF+);

¹³ https://competition-policy.ec.europa.eu/state-aid/legislation/regulations_en

¹⁴ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/horizon-europe-work-programmes_en

- the Just Transition Fund (JTF);
- the European Maritime Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund (EMFAF);
- the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD);
- InvestEU; and
- private funds or financial instruments”.

3.3 Common Provisions Regulation (CPR)

TOP LINES

- The CPR underlines the need to optimise the added value and uptake of co-financed international research activities, and contains specific provisions that allow for users to benefit from streamlining the utilization of EU funds in joint calls.
- General principle of the CPR: the eligibility of the expenditure is determined on the basis of national rules, except where specific rules are laid down in the EU legal framework.
 - Simplification compared to the predefined measures (2014-2020), flexible framework for MS.
- Financial contributions under programmes co-financed by the ERDF, the ESF+, the EMFAF and the EAFRD may be considered as a contribution of the participating MS to European Partnerships.

A Common Provisions Regulation (CPR) is established to govern 8 EU funds (Regulation (EU) 2021/1060 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 June 2021), alongside specific regulations pertaining to each fund. This regulatory framework delineates comprehensive guidelines for the programming, management, and oversight of these funds, encompassing various stages such as application, evaluation, selection, decision-making, payment processes, as well as reporting and control mechanisms. The delivery of these funds is shared with MS and regions. Together, they represent a third of the EU budget.

The 8 funds covered by this common regulation are:

- European Regional Development Fund (ERDF);

- European Social Fund Plus (ESF+);
- Cohesion Fund (CF);
- Just Transition Fund (JTF);
- European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund (EMFAF);
- Asylum and Migration Fund (AMIF);
- Internal Security Fund (ISF);
- Border Management and Visa Instrument (BMVI).

The first four of these programmes (ERDF, ESF+, CF and JTF) are under the Cohesion Policy¹⁵.

The largest share of this budget is allocated to 5 common policy objectives:

- a more competitive and smarter Europe by promoting innovative and smart economic transformation and regional ICT connectivity;
- a greener, low-carbon transitioning towards a net zero carbon economy and resilient Europe by promoting clean and fair energy transition, green and blue investment, the circular economy, climate change mitigation and adaptation, risk prevention and management, and sustainable urban mobility;
- a more connected Europe by enhancing mobility;
- a more social and inclusive Europe implementing the European Pillar of Social Rights;
- a Europe closer to citizens by fostering the sustainable and integrated development of all types of territories and local initiatives.

A desk analysis of funds across MS was presented in Deliverable 8.1. Each fund has specific objectives defined in their respective fund-specific regulations. Synergies should be ensured with the funds and other relevant instruments, namely HE, and other international research programmes. These synergies should be achieved through user-friendly key mechanisms,

¹⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/policy/what/investment-policy_en

namely the possibility of combining funding from different Union instruments in the same operation as long as double financing is avoided. Each MS should have the flexibility to contribute to international research funding programmes' joint calls, under certain conditions set out in the CPR. Both HE regulations and the CPR highlight the feasibility and desirability of this approach. However, the synergetic implementation must adhere to the same protocols as standard procedures.

Common Provisions Regulation:

“Member States and the Commission shall promote the coordination, complementarity and coherence between the Funds and other Union instruments and funds. They shall optimise mechanisms for coordination between those responsible to avoid duplication during planning and implementation. Accordingly, Member States and the Commission shall also take into account the relevant country-specific recommendations in the programming and implementation of the Funds.”

“In order to optimise the added value from investments funded wholly or in part through the budget of the Union, synergies should be sought in particular between the Funds and other relevant instruments, including the Recovery and Resilience Facility and the Brexit Adjustment Reserve. Those synergies should be achieved through user-friendly key mechanisms, namely the recognition of flat rates for eligible costs from Horizon Europe for a similar operation and the possibility of combining funding from different Union instruments in the same operation as long as double financing is avoided. This Regulation should therefore set out rules for complementary financing from the Funds.”

3.4 Challenges

TOP LINES

The following challenges for streamlining funding synergies between EU funds and co-funded research and innovation programmes have been identified:

- Lack of clear EC guidelines as to how to manage synergies.
- Combination of different funding rules and procedures:

- Different provisions in the regulations of each fund/mechanism (i.e., Common Provisions Regulation for European Structural and Investment Funds, RRF regulation, etc.).
- Different procedures (sets of rules) and obligations (indicators, reporting obligations, reporting tools, audit requirements), creating administrative burden and additional human resources requirements.
- Issues on the conformity of RDI joint call actions and national EU co-funded programme and legislation.
- Designing efficient and effective funding schemes (as well as overseeing the implementation of projects) within the designated timelines requires swift action.
- Need for revision of national legal frameworks.
- Taking into account state aid rules (e.g., participation of large enterprises)

Currently, to the best of our knowledge, only few MS have expressed interest in using EU funds in joint calls. A major reason for this low interest may be the lack of clear processes to use EU funds in joint research activities. Although guidelines are available in the HE regulation, such as the provision of processes concerning ERDF in the HE Regulation, provided by the EC in 2022, the current EU regulation framework (CPR and fund specific regulations) does not establish any derogation to use EU funds in international R&D&I joint funding calls.

On the practical side, managing EU contributions from HE funding alongside national EU co-funded programmes introduces significant complexities, primarily due to double reporting requirements. National/regional EU co-funded programmes are managed electronically within national/regional IT systems, posing challenges for seamless integration of HE funding contributions into existing electronic decision-making and payment systems. Consequently, HE funding contributions must undergo separate management by distinct public bodies, exacerbating administrative burdens through duplicated decision-making and reporting processes. This pitfall places undue strain on both administrative entities and beneficiaries alike.

An additional aspect to highlight is the temporal constraints. Typically, research projects selected for funding span a minimum of three years. Considering that the eligibility period for current specific EU structural funds concludes by the end of 2029, all projects must be finalised and payments disbursed to the final beneficiaries by then. Consequently, research projects funded through national EU co-funded programmes should ideally commence by 2026 to ensure timely completion. However, delays in EU legislation often result in national EU co-funded programmes commencing 2-3 years later. Consequently, MS have only a brief window to utilize these programmes for joint research activities.

Specifically managing co-funded European Partnerships (EP) presents a set of challenges, particularly regarding ERDF national reporting on certified expenses. This includes varying co-funding rates across different European Partnerships, which depend on the Consortium Agreement among participants. Additionally, the final co-funding rate is often determined after the projects have been either selected, or even completed and reporting has concluded. Furthermore, the timelines for disbursing co-funding payments vary among European Partnerships.

Despite the challenges outlined above, there are noteworthy cases of practical steps taken to make these synergies operational. Remarkably, calls for proposal have already been launched, and projects have been selected under such co-funding schemes. Insights on this matter is provided in the following subsections.

3.5 European Structural and Investment Funds (ESIFs)

The ESI Funds comprise of:

- the European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund;
- the European Regional Development Fund;
- the European Social Fund;
- the Cohesion Fund;
- the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development.

Understanding how a project can be co-financed by two instruments poses a major challenge. Beyond familiarity with the frameworks involved, practical experience in implementing a co-funded project using both HE and a European Structural and Investment (ESI) fund is important for managing authorities. To shed light on this matter, we provide an illustrative example of synergies within co-funded European Partnerships in the box below, while concrete implementations of synergies are detailed in the country-specific subsections throughout this document.

Future synergies within Co-Funded European Partnerships: practical illustrative example (ERDF)

1. A Member State/region participates in a consortium comprising national funding bodies.
2. It proposes to use an ERDF programme to cover part of the national contribution to the Partnership.
3. The national funding body acting as the ERDF programme intermediate body reports to HE that it is providing financial support/funding to its beneficiaries amounting to e.g., €100 million. The national funding body receives e.g., a 30% reimbursement from HE (€30 million).
4. The remaining €70 million can be co-funded from the ERDF programme (e.g. with a 50% co-funding rate). The co-financing rate of the programme priority must be respected (CPR, Article 112).
5. The total cost of €100 million would therefore be covered as follows: €30 million from HE, €35 million from the ERDF and €35 million from the national budget.
6. Expenditure and costs must be declared and reported in accordance with the rules for cumulative funding.

3.5.1 European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund (EMFAF)

TOP LINES

- The EMFAF Regulation entered into force in July 2021. Most of the financial resources are implemented through national programmes prepared by Member States and approved by the Commission. All national programmes are now adopted.
- The budget of EMFAF is broken down into shared and direct management of funds, each with its own set of conditions.

- General principles for shared management in the EMFAF regulation: MS may select operations which 1) contribute to the specific objectives of the fund and 2) are not explicitly ineligible.

3.5.1.1 Scope

The EMFAF¹⁶ supports the EU common fisheries policy (CFP), the EU maritime policy and the EU agenda for international ocean governance. It provides financial support for developing innovative projects ensuring that aquatic and maritime resources are used sustainably. It also helps achieve the UN's Sustainable Development Goal 14 ('conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas and marine resources'), to which the EU is committed. The EMFAF helps fulfil the objectives of the European Green Deal, i.e. the roadmap for the EU climate and environmental policies. It is complemented by specific funding for the European Fisheries Control Agency, for the sustainable fisheries partnership agreements (SFPAs) and for the EU membership to regional fisheries management organisations (RFMOs) and other international organisations.

The EMFAF focuses on enabling conditions for the development of **a sustainable blue economy** and on removing bottlenecks to facilitate investment in new markets, technologies and services. It supports:

- maritime governance to coordinate human activities at sea in a sustainable manner (e.g. through 'maritime spatial planning');
- the transfer and uptake of research, innovation and technology in private investment;
- the development of maritime skills;
- the dissemination of marine and maritime environmental and socio-economic data;
- the development of project pipelines to leverage private investment.

¹⁶ https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/eu-budget/performance-and-reporting/programme-performance-statements/european-maritime-fisheries-and-aquaculture-fund-performance_en

The implementation of EMFAF varies significantly across MS. For instance, in some countries, such as Italy, it operates at the regional level. As such, there is no “one fits all” solution for a coordination framework. For instance, in Finland, where the managing authority of EMFAF is a SBEP partner, coordination in the scope of the Partnership is streamlined, particularly concerning call procedures. However, in other countries, SBEP may need to engage with local or regional entities to enable the implementation of calls and other actions. Despite the differences, there are common issues that may encourage managing authorities to exchange solutions and learn from one another, and here we aim to facilitate this process.

3.5.1.2 Financial framework: shared and direct management

The EMFAF is programmed for 2021-2027 with a budget of €6.108 billion, broken down as follows¹⁷:

- €5.311 billion (87%) implemented under shared management. This budget is provided through national programmes co-financed by EU budget and EU countries, for which the Common Provisions Regulation 2021-2027 is applicable. In order to use this shared management budget, MS must prepare national programmes (details in Subsection 3.5.1.2.1) that must be approved by the European Commission.
- €797 million (13%) implemented under direct management. This amount is provided directly by the Commission. This budget is spent and managed by the European Commission. The Commission prepares annual work programmes which detail the allocation of this budget. These work programmes are discussed and approved in the EMFAF Committee, which is composed by experts from the MS.

The EMFAF has a set of four priorities pre-defined by the EU:

- Priority 1. Fostering sustainable fisheries and the restoration and conservation of aquatic biological resources (51% of shared management budget);

¹⁷ https://oceans-and-fisheries.ec.europa.eu/funding/emfaf_en

- Priority 2. Fostering sustainable aquaculture activities, and processing and marketing of fisheries and aquaculture products, thus contributing to food security in the Union (35% of shared management budget);
- Priority 3. Enabling a sustainable blue economy in coastal, island and inland areas, and fostering the development of fishing and aquaculture communities (10% of shared management budget);
- Priority 4. Strengthening international Ocean governance and enabling seas and oceans to be safe, secure, clean and sustainably managed. (2% of shared management budget).

Under the shared management, each of these four priorities has their own specific objectives, whereas the Commission has a different focus these priorities, and each priority has a set of scope items under direct management. For priorities 1 and 2, which cover by far most of the budget, and may be the main focus when seeking synergies between EMFAF and HE, their specific objectives under shared management and scope under direct management are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Specific objectives under shared management and scope under direct management for priorities 1 and 2.

Priority	Specific objectives under shared management	Scope under direct management
1. Fostering sustainable fisheries and the restoration and conservation of aquatic biological resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthening economically, socially and environmentally sustainable fishing activities • Increasing energy efficiency and reducing CO2 emissions through the replacement or modernisation of engines of fishing vessels • Promoting the adjustment of fishing capacity to fishing opportunities in cases of permanent cessation of fishing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provision of scientific advice and knowledge for the purpose of promoting sound and efficient fisheries management decisions under the CFP • Regional cooperation on conservation measures • Development and implementation of a Union fisheries control system

	<p>activities and contributing to a fair standard of living in cases of temporary cessation of fishing activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Fostering efficient fisheries control and enforcement, including fighting against IUU fishing, as well as reliable data for knowledge-based decision-making ● Promoting a level-playing field for fishery and aquaculture products from the outermost regions ● Contributing to the protection and restoration of aquatic biodiversity and ecosystems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Functioning of Advisory Councils ● Voluntary contributions to the activities of international organisations dealing with fisheries ● Promotion of clean and healthy seas and oceans
<p>2. Fostering sustainable aquaculture activities, and processing and marketing of fisheries and aquaculture products, thus contributing to food security in the Union</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Promoting sustainable aquaculture activities, especially strengthening the competitiveness of aquaculture production while ensuring that the activities are environmentally sustainable in the long term ● Promoting marketing, quality and value added of fisheries and aquaculture products, as well as processing of these products 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Development and dissemination of market intelligence for fishery and aquaculture products by the Commission

3.5.1.2.1 Framework under shared management

It is important to consider the architectural framework (Figure 1) when strategizing the utilisation of EMFAF. EMFAF operates within a structured hierarchy comprising three key layers:

1. Priorities: These set the overarching direction.
2. Specific Objectives: Detailed in the EMFAF regulation, they further delineate the focus areas.
3. Types of Interventions: MS must specify where funds will be allocated.

MS are tasked with preparing the union-level priority, which includes conducting a SWOT analysis, and identifying specific needs based on this analysis. Subsequently, they select specific objectives for inclusion in their operational programmes, and detail the types of actions to be funded, target beneficiaries, financial allocations, co-financing rates, and anticipated outputs and results.

Figure 1. Framework for strategizing national programmes (under shared management). (Courtesy of DG MARE, adapted).

3.5.1.3 Conditions of support

The following general principles of eligibility are applicable:

- **General Principle in the Common Provisions Regulation:** The eligibility of expenditure is determined on the basis of national rules, except where specific rules are laid down in the Union legal framework.

- General principles for shared management in the EMFAF: MS may support operations which:
 - Fall under the scope of the Priorities and Specific Objectives.
 - Are not explicitly ineligible.
 - Are in accordance with applicable Union law.

Ineligible operations and limitations are also specified in the EMFAF Regulation¹⁸. For instance, construction, acquisition, and importation of fishing vessels is ineligible, unless otherwise provided for in the regulation. There are also specific conditions regarding the capacity and engine of fishing vessels (see illustrative examples in the box below). As such, there might be no exemption for the case of R&I projects.

EMFAF sets very detailed rules concerning operations related to fishing vessels. For instance, a research project focusing on energy transition within the fishing industry is restricted to utilizing existing fishing vessels, precluding for example the possibility of funding a public project aimed at prototyping a small-scale electric fishing vessel and conducting pilot tests. Similarly, research and development projects aimed at developing new engine solutions for fishing vessels must adhere to the same rigorous conditions as standard EMFAF private investment projects. Moreover, if the national fishing fleet fails to align with available fishing opportunities, the entire fishing segment becomes ineligible for funding. These regulations significantly limit the scope of potential research, development, and innovation actions for fishing vessels.

3.5.1.4 Implementation in Finland

As previously discussed, the aim of having synergies between different funding sources is clearly specified, in the Recital of the Common Provisions Regulation. And it is possible to combine funding from different Union instruments in the same operation, as long as double

¹⁸ https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=uriserv:OJ.L_.2021.247.01.0001.01.ENG

financing is avoided. Yet, no specific procedural guidelines are provided for EMFAF in the regulations, despite it being a target of these synergies. Therefore, it is crucial for the managing authority of the funding in the MS/region to adhere to the same procedures as those employed in regular project financing. In this context, three potential pitfalls must be considered when utilizing this fund in co-funded calls, concerning the (1) selection procedures for operations, (2) the coordination of calls for proposals, and (3) the implementation of EU top-up funding.

In the case of Finland, the synergistic implementation of HE with EMFAF leverages on the countries pre-existing frameworks. These frameworks have previously enabled joint funding for projects, where, for example, a municipality contributes (with e.g., 20% of the funding) alongside with EMFAF (which would cover the remaining 80%). This arrangement involves two separate granting decisions. During the payment phase, the EMFAF authority verifies total costs and disburses the fund (80% of the amount in the current example), while the municipality's share is managed through a distinct financing stream.

The coordination between EMFAF and Horizon Europe in Finland follows a similar model. For instance, if the EU top-up funding is 30%, EMFAF can cover 70% of the total eligible costs. In Finland, the management of EU top-up funding falls under the jurisdiction of the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry, a SBEP partner, which verifies total costs and covers e.g., 30% of them. Therefore, the implementation of this system represents a continuation of existing practices in Finland.

3.5.1.4.1 Selection of operations

This concerns the procedure for selecting operations by the managing authority (the term 'operation' is used in the cohesion policy context). The CPR Art. 73 states that

“For the selection of operations, the managing authority shall establish and apply criteria and procedures which are non-discriminatory, transparent (···)” and “The criteria and procedures shall ensure that the operations to be selected are prioritised with a view to maximising the contribution of Union funding towards the achievement of the objectives of the programme.”

In conformity, the Finland national EMFAF programme established the following four strategic objectives:

1. Supporting sustainable growth in the fisheries sector
2. Safeguarding the preconditions for primary production
3. Accelerating innovations and renewal of the fisheries sector
4. Strong focus on environmental issues

Additionally, and particularly aligned with objective 3 above, the Finnish national EMFAF programme strategy states that it is their aim to increase international cooperation in research and development, and funding from the EMFAF programme may complement the objectives of HE. Also, this funding can be used as national contribution, including for international calls. It is therefore clearly stated that the Finland EMFAF programme intends to use national funds to boost this kind of joint international calls.

Finnish EMFAF programme's strategy: "The aim is also to increase international cooperation in R&D. The Horizon Europe 2021-2027 offers opportunities for international cooperation, including in fisheries. Funding from the EMFAF programme may complement the objectives of Horizon Europe. Synergies will be sought with the EU Mission Restore Our Ocean and Waters by 2030, in particular as regards aquaculture and the multifunctionality of marine areas. EMFAF funding can be used as a national contribution for international calls."

Moreover, in the description of types of actions concerning R&D&I, it was included that funding can be used as a national contribution to international calls, such that the Finnish EMFAF Programme can participate and contribute to joint calls with Horizon Europe.

"Funding can be used as a national contribution to international coordinated calls, so that the programme can finance the costs of Finnish actors (e.g. Nordic calls and EU Horizon)".

Regarding selection criteria and methodology, the monitoring committee has adopted the national methodology for selection of operations and selection criteria, where it is stated the possibilities of using either **continuous calls** or **fixed-term application procedures**. In case of fixed-term application procedure, a project can be selected based on the selection criteria in

accordance with the objectives of the call. As such, targeted calls can be launched and specific criteria can be adopted for this kind of call. Also, a specific selection criterion concerning the selection in an international call was introduced for this kind of co-funded application.

National methodology for selection of operations: “Where the selection of a project is based on a fixed-term application procedure, the selection of projects shall be based on the selection criteria in accordance with the objectives of the call. The objective of the call for applications and the selection criteria applicable to it, as well as the programme measure concerning the application procedure, shall be indicated in the call for applications.”

Specific selection criteria for co-funded applications: “The project has been selected for funding in an international call.”

3.5.1.4.2 Coordination of calls for proposals

Regarding the calls for proposals, the CPR states that the managing authority must publish a website concerning the fund and, among other obligations, they must also publish a timetable of the planned calls for proposals that must be updated accordingly.

CPR, Article 49: “1. The managing authority shall ensure that, within 6 months of the decision approving the programme, there is a website where information on programmes under its responsibility is available, covering the programme’s objectives, activities, available funding opportunities and achievements.” “2. The managing authority shall ensure the publication on the website referred to in paragraph 1 (···) of a timetable of the planned calls for proposals, that is updated at least three times a year (···).”

Figure 2 presents an example of a timeline with EMFAF as a co-financing instrument with SBEP 1st call for proposals which follows the selection procedure as specified in the CPR. Prior to the launch of SBEP call, the local managing authorities would 1) reserve a specific budget for the concerning topics. Then, once SBEP call is launched, or even beforehand, the concerning authority would 2) publish the timetable of the planned calls for proposals in the EMFAF website. Afterwards, once the selection procedure on the SBEP side is in its late

phase, with the selection of proposals, then the managing authority would 3) open a target call for proposals that were selected in the SBEP call.

Figure 2. Example of parallel timelines for joint calls (Adapted from ‘Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry of Finland’).

3.5.1.4.3 EU top-up funding in projects co-funded by EMFAF

EMFAF projects often involve additional public financing, a common practice seen, for instance, in Finland where national projects may receive funding from municipalities or research institutes within the same operational project. In the context of EU legislation, there are no restrictions on combining EMFAF and EU top-up funding (or other combination of EU funding streams), provided that there is no duplication of financing within a single project.

EU top-up funding cannot be managed within the Finnish EMFAF IT system. Consequently, they have opted to employ a model where the EMFAF intermediate body (ELY centres) responsible for all funding decisions within their fund, oversees the grant decision-making model regarding the EMFAF.

Under this planned model, schematized in Figure 3, the EMFAF intermediate body grants the EMFAF funding rate, e.g., 70%, while e.g., the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry handles EU top-up funding and disburses it to beneficiaries (30%). Payments to beneficiaries are

calculated based on total costs using a real cost model. Beneficiaries apply for funding from both the intermediate body and the ministry, and both entities verify the total cost to avoid double financing.

Figure 3. Possible funding scheme for a project including both EU top-up financing and EMFAF financing.

3.5.1.4.4 Creating additional synergies between different funding instruments

To enhance additional funding synergies, Finland has identified three desired outcomes to pursue: 1) communication and dissemination of results within the sector and among stakeholders, 2) transformation of research results into practice in enterprises and private sector, and 3) facilitation of public-private partnerships.

To boost innovations, Finland national EMFAF relies first on traditional methods to finance public and collective development projects, spanning from local to national projects. These funds are allocated towards research infrastructure, including the construction of new facilities, and co-funded international joint projects. Additionally, Finland has introduced innovative financing products tailored for enterprises. Among these is the ‘innovation voucher,’ offering a modest sum, such as €5.000,00, with minimal administrative burdens. Enterprises can utilize this fund with flexibility to boost novel ideas within their operations. Beyond this, a more substantial financing option exists in the form of development funding for companies, with a maximum allocation of €200.000,00. Furthermore, at the enterprise level, Finland provides opportunities for increased aid intensity for investments conducted in collaboration with research institutes, thereby fostering robust public-private partnerships at a tangible

level. Lastly, they have initiated the **'Fisheries Innovation Programmes'** in previous programmes.

The underlying principle behind these innovation programmes was a shift from project-based development approaches to a target-oriented and continuous long-term development model. In a traditional development approach, calls for proposals are opened, projects are initiated as planned, but often encounter the need for further research or development, leading to a cycle of new projects. This process often causes a decline in trust and commitment among stakeholders, along with time gaps and discontinuities in development efforts. To address it, Finland transitioned towards a 'learning networks' model. Here, main actors from both public and private sectors collaborate to design and agree upon shared visions and goals. Through continuous collaboration, trust and commitment among these actors grow, allowing for sustained progress towards common objectives. Ideally, this cooperative approach fosters innovation and utilization of innovations collectively, surpassing the innovation levels achievable through traditional methods. After approximately five years of implementation, these innovation programmes have yielded favourable outcomes. For instance, the 'Aquaculture Innovation Programme' successfully engaged relevant national institutes, including research institutions, universities, and aquaculture companies.

There is a commitment to continue these innovation programmes, which are built upon robust public-private partnerships, and the focus will be on digital and green transition and sustainable growth of the fisheries sector. Five innovation programmes will be launched, one of them centred on fisheries (the 'Fisheries Environmental Programme'). These programmes will formulate and regularly update Research & Development & Innovation agendas, guiding funding and other national research activities towards jointly identified goals aligned with the overarching vision.

Primarily funded by (European) EMFAF funds, these programmes will also leverage other national and international financing opportunities to achieve their objectives comprehensively. In the case of Finland, it is anticipated that these platforms will serve to enhance synergies

among various funding instruments, particularly by disseminating information and catalysing additional research and innovation activities at the national level.

3.5.2 European Regional Development Fund (ERDF)

TOP LINES

Synergies with Horizon Europe:

- Synergies in European Partnerships: ERDF as MS contribution in Horizon Europe Partnerships (Co-funded & Institutionalised ones)
- The ERDF programme contributions to European Partnerships must comply with the rules on the prohibition of the double declaration of expenditure laid down in Article 63(9) CPR.
- Commission Notice: Synergies between Horizon Europe and ERDF programmes (2022/C 421/03)¹⁹.

3.5.2.1 Scope

The ERDF focuses, among other things, on the development and strengthening of regional and local R&I ecosystems, networks and industrial transformation, including support to building R&I capacities, to the take-up of results and to the rolling out of novel technologies and innovative and climate-friendly solutions from the framework programmes for R&I through the ERDF. Being one of the main investment instruments within the framework of the Cohesion Policy, it works to strengthen the economic, social and territorial cohesion of the European Union and correct imbalances between its regions, with 5 strategic priorities for 2021-2027 to make Europe smarter, greener, more connected, more social, and closer to its citizens.

¹⁹ https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=uriserv%3AOJ.C_.2022.421.01.0007.01.ENG&toc=OJ%3AC%3A2022%3A421%3AFULL / https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/information-sources/publications/communications/2022/synergies-between-erdf-programmes-and-horizon-europe_en

3.5.2.2 Synergies in European Partnerships

Research, Technology, Development and Innovation (RTDI) interventions under the Partnership Agreement 2021-2027 are subject to the provisions of regulation (EU) 2021/1058 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 June 2021 on the European Regional Development Fund and on the Cohesion Fund.

Support to Partnerships via ERDF as a MS contribution stands as a major incentive for the participation of regional actors and alignment with common EU priorities within HE Partnerships. Key considerations include:

- ERDF may function as a MS contribution to European Partnerships, contingent upon compliance with relevant CPR-provisions and fund-specific regulations.
- Bodies implementing the partnership must be designated as ERDF intermediate bodies, as stipulated by the CPR.
- MS may decide to provide support directly to operations selected under the partnership, as stipulated by the CPR.
- Specific administrative steps ensure compliance with the requirement to prevent double declaration of costs.
- Alignment of S3 is an eligibility condition for the ERDF programmes (see box below).

From Commission notice – Synergies between HE and ERDF Programmes:

“Smart specialisation strategies (S3) are crucial for synergies with smart growth-related instruments at EU level (especially with HE). Bottom-up S3 priority-setting should make it easier to find partners in other Member States with a view to cooperating on related topics and value chains.”

“With respect to the ERDF, Article 11(1)(b)(iii) of the Common Provisions Regulation (CPR)⁵ requires Member States to specify in their strategic partnership agreements: ‘complementarities and synergies between the funds covered by the Partnership Agreement [...] and other Union instruments [...] and, where appropriate, projects funded under Horizon Europe’. Similarly, for each cohesion policy programme, Article 22(3)(a)(iii) CPR requires a summary of the main challenges, considering ‘investment needs and complementarity and synergies with other forms of support’.”

3.5.2.3 Implementation in Emilia-Romagna

The regional strategy for innovation is shaped by the regional Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) which Emilia-Romagna (Italy) has drawn by crossing the grand socio-technical challenges with the most relevant value chains, resulting in 15 cross-cutting thematic areas, with **Blue Growth** being among them.

The Emilia-Romagna ERDF Regional Programme (ERDF RP)²⁰ for the period 2021-2027 is the programming document that defines strategy and operations for the use of funds allocated to the Region by the ERDF. In close coherence with main European and national strategies identifying green and digital transition as core pillars for economic and social growth, the Regional Programme Strategy follows the priorities outlined in the national Partnership Agreement and the main regional framework strategies amongst which the Regional Pact for Work and Climate. It has four main priorities – Policy Objectives, each of which has various Specific Objectives and different implementing Actions:

- Research, innovation, competitiveness (detailed in the Subsection 3.5.2.3.1)
- Sustainability, decarbonisation, biodiversity, resilience
- Sustainable mobility and air quality
- Attractiveness, cohesion, local development.

This list is completed by Technical Assistance, a fundamental element for an effective Programme management.

The Regional Programme supports a revitalisation process that combines quality of work, increased productivity and added value, technological, environmental and social innovation, attractiveness and international openness. Thus, it helps the regional system on its path towards green transition and digital transformation, helping to reduce economic, social, gender, generational and territorial inequalities.

²⁰ <https://fesr.regione.emilia-romagna.it/erdf>

Over 1 billion euro – €1.024.200.000 – are planned for the implementation of the 2021-2027 ERDF Emilia-Romagna Regional Programme, a third of which will be allocated to fight against climate change.

3.5.2.3.1 Research, innovation, competitiveness

A total of 530 million euro is available for this implementation action, corresponding to 52% of 2021-2027 ERDF Regional Programme financial allocation. It addresses advanced research and innovation policy, with a focus on local specificities, and responds to three major challenges:

- innovative and smart transition, closely related to the new S3 Strategy, which indicates the guidelines for the regional research and innovation policy;
- promoting digital transformation to improve opportunities for economic growth and social innovation, stimulating a cultural change and making digital a new territorial peculiarity;
- boosting competitiveness within the regional production system by focusing on labour, the value of enterprise and the entrepreneurial and widespread pluralism of SMEs.

3.5.2.3.2 SBEP call/ERDF call

The Emilia-Romagna Region (Regione Emilia Romagna) is one of the 38 funding organizations of the second SBEP Joint Transnational Co-Funded Call “Unified paths to a climate-neutral, sustainable, and resilient blue economy: engaging civil society, academia, policy, and industry”, launched in February 2024. As per specified in the Call documents, the Emilia-Romagna Region stands alone among these funding organizations in its inclusion of **ERDF-EMFAF** as a co-funding stream.

To materialize this type co-funding scheme, coherence and complementarity should be ensured, specifically:

- Coordination of the strategic priorities of the different funding programmes from their conception to promote a common vision,

- Adoption of a strategic approach in the use of European funding.

Additionally, for this form of synergy,

1. the rules of the respective programme shall apply to each contribution;
2. cumulative funding must not exceed total costs eligible;
3. the support provided by the different programmes can be calculated pro-rata;
4. the conditions of support for beneficiaries are illustrated in a specific document.

As such, the project shall be consistent with the strategy, contents and specific objective of the Emilia-Romagna ERDF 2021-2027 Regional Programme, and the Emilia-Romagna Smart Specialization Strategy 2021-2027, as specified in the text of the second SBEP Joint Transnational Co-Funded Call.

3.5.2.4 Implementation in Malta

The **transfer** between cohesion policy funds and Horizon Europe is one of the new possibilities available in the 2021-2027 programming period in the context of synergies between EU funding sources. These transfers give an opportunity to MS to strengthen participation in HE where traditionally it has been low and to improve their success rate; to boost projects in areas identified as priorities through smart specialization; and to preserve administrative capacity at national/regional level in the selection and follow-up of R&I projects.

Malta has been the first MS to make use of this possibility, by asking to transfer 5 million euro from ERDF to HE between 2023 and 2027. As a result of the transfer, for the first 2023 batch of transfer, five Maltese ERA fellowships, initially not selected for funding by HE due to lack of sufficient budget, will now be financed thanks to the ERDF resources that Malta's authorities decided to transfer to HE. These are the first projects funded with the transfer from ERDF to HE. The Grant Agreements for these 5 projects were signed in February 2024, following the normal HE project cycle.

These projects will support the strengthening of the Maltese R&I system and will help to attract new talent in the country as the University of Malta will be able to host five additional researchers.

3.5.2.5 Implementation in Greece

Development planning for the 2021-2027 programming period is primarily based on the **Strategy for Smart Specialization** established at the national and regional levels, and directs all RTDI interventions funded by the ERDF.

The GSRI (General Secretariat for Research and Innovation)²¹, is tasked with designing RTDI interventions under the 2021-2027 Programming Period, and in this context participates in

- Designing the Smart Specialization Strategy 2021-2027 in cooperation with the General Secretariat for Industry and under the coordination of the General Secretariat of Public Investment and NSRF, in conformity with Article 36 of Law 4712/2020.
- Designing the RTDI interventions under the “Competitiveness” Operational Programme 2021-2027, which is the principal financial instrument to support research and innovation during this Programming Period.

The strategic objectives set for the Smart Specialization Strategy 2021-2027 are:

- Production of New Knowledge;
- Commercialization and diffusion of Knowledge;
- Technological Transformation of the Greek Productive Sector – Innovation adoption;
- Internationalization – Penetration into Global Value Chains.

3.5.2.6 Implementation in Cyprus

The Research and Innovation Foundation (RIF) administers SBEP’s Calls for Proposals in Cyprus, where they are co-financed by the Republic of Cyprus and the European Regional

²¹ <https://gsri.gov.gr/en/programming-periods/>

Development Fund (ERDF) under the Operational Programme “**ΘΑΛΕΙΑ**” 2021-2027. These calls fall under Priority 1: “Competitive, Smart and Digital Economy” and the Specific Objective (1i): “Developing and enhancing research and innovation capacities and the uptake of advanced technologies.” Furthermore, they are part of the “European Partnerships” Programme within the framework of the “RESTART 2016-2020” Programmes for Research, Technological Development and Innovation. RIF has established a unified set of rules (where possible) and a single electronic platform²² to streamline the application process, regardless of the funding source. Also, close co-operation and co-ordination between all national stakeholders has been encouraged to counter the challenges in implementing co-funding schemes.

The design of RESTART Programmes 2016-2020 focuses on particular objectives, as well as on the Priority Sectors identified through the Smart Specialisation Strategy for Cyprus (S3Cy). At the same time, it is part of the Operational Programme “Competitiveness and Sustainable Development 2014-2020”, which is the development strategy of Cyprus for the utilisation of the resources of ERDF within the framework of Priority Axis 1: “Strengthening the Competitiveness of Cyprus Economy”. The multiannual legal and regulatory framework of the RESTART Programmes 2016-2020 are aligned with the Smart Specialization Strategy (2015 strategy, revised in 2023).

3.6 Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF)

Regulation (EU) 2021/241 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 February 2021 establishes a Recovery and Resilience Facility Plan (RRF) and sets out the facility’s aims and the criteria for receiving funding.

3.6.1 Implementation in Italy

The National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP) of Italy is based on Next Generation EU, a programme that provides investments and reforms to accelerate the green and digital

²² <https://iris.research.org.cy/#!/calls>

transition, improve worker training, and achieve gender, territorial, and generational equality. All the investments and reforms contained in the NRRP are divided in 6 specific missions, subdivided in specific components.

Within the framework of NRRP, the Ministry of Enterprises and Made in Italy (MIMIT) received €200.000.000,00 to fund Mission 4 (Education and Research), Component 2 (From Research to Enterprise), Investment 2.2 (Horizon Europe Partnerships), and allocated this budget to seven European partnerships, especially digital and green partnerships, including SBEP.

The MIMIT participates in SBEP as national funding organization. In the first call (2023) it provided €10.000.000,00 for contribution to the call and €800.000,00 for maximum funding per awarded project. For the second call (2024), MIMIT withdraw the participation due to uncertain procedure of costs reporting towards the EU granting authority, not guaranteeing the full eligibility of funding.

3.6.2 Implementation in Greece

The GSRI (General Secretariat for Research and Innovation) is responsible for implementing RTDI actions under the “Greece 2.0” National Recovery and Resilience Plan. Recovery Fund actions, with a budget of €444 million, address country-specific research and innovation needs which are not covered by the Partnership Agreement for regulatory reasons, such as basic research, or are related to important RTDI infrastructures with financial requirements exceeding the available PA budget, or result from geographical restrictions imposed by the PA that create insurmountable obstacles in terms of funding allocation.

Elevate Greece²³ represents a noteworthy example of synergy between RRF and National funding. It is an initiative launched by the Greek Government with a mission to identify promising startups and support their growth, in order to ultimately build a robust innovation ecosystem. The initiative provides a digital gate through which Greek startups can apply requesting to be officially accredited by competent State Ministry (Ministry of Development

²³ <https://elevategreece.gov.gr/>

& Investments –GSRI). The National Startup Registry is the official record of startups in Greece. It aims at monitoring startup entrepreneurship progress based on specific KPIs, at supporting them with benefits and incentives, and to operate as a dashboard of metrics to attract investors from Greece and abroad.

3.7 InvestEU Programme

The InvestEU Programme²⁴ supports sustainable investment, innovation and job creation in Europe. With the EU budget guarantee provided to International and National promotional banks, the InvestEU programme aims to trigger more than €372 billion in private investments to high EU policy priority areas.

Regulation (EU) 2021/523 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 March 2021²⁵ establishes the InvestEU Programme and amends Regulation (EU) 2015/1017. Specific contents of this regulation are highlighted in the box below.

Regulation (EU) 2021/523:

n. 4 “Member states (...) develop their own national multiannual investment strategies in support of those reform priorities. Those (...) priority investment projects that are to be supported by national funding, Union funding, or both. Those strategies should also use Union funding in a coherent manner and maximise the added value of the financial support to be received in particular from the European structural and investment funds, the Recovery and Resilience Facility established by Regulation (EU) 2021/241 of the European Parliament and of the Council and the InvestEU Programme”.

Annex II includes “Areas eligible for financing and investment operations” into InvestEU Programme:

“5) research, development and innovation, in particular through:

²⁴ https://investeu.europa.eu/investeu-programme_en

²⁵ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2021/523/oj>

- a) research and innovation projects that contribute to the objectives of Horizon Europe, including research infrastructure and support to academia;
 - d) collaborative research and innovation projects involving academia, research and innovation organisations and industry; public-private partnerships and civil society organisations;
- 6) the development, deployment and scaling-up of digital technologies and services, especially digital technologies and services, including media, online service platforms and secure digital communication, that contribute to the objectives of the Digital Europe Programme, in particular through:
- i) advanced digital technologies and services contributing to the digitisation of the Union industry and the integration of digital technologies, services and skills in the transport sector of the Union”.

The current CPR sets specific rules for the allocation of national EU funding to the InvestEU Programme and to financial instruments. In the case of InvestEU, MS can reserve national programme funding to this specific purpose and transfer budget to the European Investment Bank group (EIB). The EIB then utilises this funding based on its rules and procedures. Similarly, MS can steer financing to so called “financial instruments”, entailing the establishment of a fund in which MS’s financial intermediate (e.g. bank) may provide loans, guarantees or equity investments. These financial instruments have specific rules and are managed outside of MS’ national programme IT systems.

Common Provisions Regulation, Article 14:

“Use of the ERDF, the ESF+, the Cohesion Fund and the EMFAF delivered through the InvestEU Programme

1. Member States may allocate, in the Partnership Agreement, an amount of up to 2% of the initial national allocation for the ERDF, the ESF+, the Cohesion Fund and the EMFAF, respectively, to be contributed to the InvestEU Programme and delivered through the EU guarantee and the InvestEU Advisory Hub in accordance with Article 10 of the InvestEU Regulation. Member States, with the agreement of the managing authority concerned, may further allocate an amount of up to 3 % of the initial national allocation of each of those Funds after 1 January 2023 through one or more programme amendment requests.”

The Partnership will support projects that are EU taxonomy compliant and qualify for financing by the EIB under the InvestEU Programme.

3.8 Synergies with other funding streams

The analysis of the complex landscape of funding mechanisms tailored to sources associated with the blue economy has showed that the most relevant instrument for the private component of the Partnership is the **BlueInvest** financing instrument.

BlueInvest²⁶ aims to boost innovation and investment in sustainable technologies for the blue economy, by supporting readiness and access to finance for early-stage businesses, Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and scale-ups. It is enabled by EMFAF and explores investment opportunities, prospects and innovation in 10 identified sectors: Aquaculture, Blue Biotechnology, Blue Renewable Energy, Blue Tech & Ocean Observation, Coastal & Maritime Tourism, Environmental Protection & Regeneration, Fisheries, Shipbuilding & Refit, Shipping & Ports, Water Management. BlueInvest is also supporting key players and enablers connect across the blue ecosystem through its community platform.

Regarding private financing, BlueInvest engages in dialogues with over 80 private investors²⁷ and has established an ecosystem aimed at bolstering blue economy startups and scaling-ups. A thorough comprehension of these mechanisms is beneficial for supporting SBEP co-funded projects in transitioning toward market uptake. Furthermore, exploring collaboration with DG MARE and BlueInvest to assess companies with high Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs) and assessing their potential integration within BlueInvest could be beneficial.

Another potential instrument for SBEP is the European Innovation Council (EIC), which includes the Pathfinder Transitional Accelerator, targeting at least TRL 5 (technology/large scale prototype must have been tested and validated in a relevant environment).

²⁶ https://maritime-forum.ec.europa.eu/theme/investments/blueinvest_en

²⁷ <https://blueinvest-community.converve.io/upload/fck/file/Blueinvest-Investor-report-An-ocean-of-opportunities.pdf>

Finally, regarding downstream funding, it does not consistently work as a “one stop shop”. In response, the Partnership must follow up and guide to the most seamless financing instrument. Given the Partnership's limitations in funding all project-worthy proposals, exploring tools such as the Seal of Excellence ²⁸ should be considered.

3.9 Proposed funding solution for the period 2028-2034

The Commission communication on Europe's 2040 climate target recognizes the need to invest in the research and demonstration, coordinating the EU and national R&I efforts, and strengthening efforts to bring innovations to the market and to scale them up. In this respect, the Commission communication underlines the need of further simplification throughout EU Programmes. EU Financial Regulation is needed for offering true one-stop shops for finance and funding opportunities, which would allow for pooling of resources, and accelerated and easier access to funds, eventually combining them with grants, reducing the number of ways to access support.

The current CPR underlines the need to optimise the added value and uptake of co-financed international research activities. Synergies should be ensured with the Funds, other relevant instruments, namely HE, and other international research programmes. These synergies should be achieved through user-friendly key mechanisms, namely the possibility of combining funding from different Union instruments in the same operation as long as double financing is avoided. Each Member State should have the flexibility to contribute to international research, development and innovation funding programmes' joint calls, under certain conditions set out in the future CPR regulation.

In consideration of the one-stop-shop model, it is imperative to streamline procedures within future EU legislation to effectively address the challenges associated with managing EU top-up funding alongside national EU funding. MS are individually responsible for the

²⁸ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/seal-excellence_en

development of IT systems, resulting in the existence of diverse and unique systems across countries. Addressing this aspect of work may prove challenging. Hence, we propose the establishment of a specific funding instrument within the regulation, described in Subsection 3.9.1.

3.9.1 Preliminary proposal for a joint funding RDI instrument

To streamline the utilization of EU funds in international research activities and establish a simplified implementation model, the feasibility of creating a dedicated funding instrument for international joint-funded research activities, akin to the existing model utilized for InvestEU and financial instruments, should be evaluated. This initiative could be carried out by establishing a regulatory framework for an "international joint funding RDI instrument," which could be overseen by national/regional research funding agencies in accordance with their respective rules and procedures. Such an approach would enable the possibility of having a one-stop-shop for funding while avoiding double reporting requirements and challenges concerning timing.

The flowchart depicted in Figure 4 outlines a potential process for managing the "joint funding RDI instrument," and the following box presents an illustrative example of how this framework could be regulated in a future CPR.

Figure 4. Scheme of a potential implementation model for the “joint funding RDI instrument”.

Regulatory framework: Example of how a “joint funding RDI instrument” could be regulated in the future CPR following the existing model concerning financial instruments.

Article (xx) Joint funding instrument for international research, development and innovation

1. Managing authorities may provide a programme contribution, from one or more funding programmes to international joint research, development and innovation funding instruments (*joint funding RDI instruments*) implemented directly by, or under the responsibility of, the managing authority which contribute to achieving specific objectives.
2. The joint funding RDI instrument shall provide support only for the operations which are selected for funding in the international joint funding RDI programmes, like EU co-funded partnerships in Horizon Europe or ERA-NETs in Horizon2020 or regional international joint research funding programmes. Such support shall be provided to costs of national final recipients, which are produced by research and development work carried out in the Member States area. Such support shall be in compliance with applicable Union State aid rules.
3. Support to final recipients may be combined with support from any Fund or another European Union instrument and may cover the same expenditure item. In such a case, the Fund’s support under the joint funding RDI instrument, shall not be declared to the Commission for support under another form, another Fund or another Union instrument.
4. The sum of all forms of combined support shall not exceed the total amount of the expenditure item concerned.

Article (xx) Implementation of joint funding RDI instruments

1. The managing authority shall set out the terms and conditions of the programme contribution to the Joint funding RDI instruments in a strategy document which shall include the elements set out in Annex x.
2. The managing authority shall select the body implementing a joint funding RDI instrument. The managing authority may directly award a contract for the implementation of a joint funding RDI instrument to a national research funding agency.
3. The terms and conditions of programme contributions to joint funding RDI instruments shall be set out in funding agreements between the duly mandated representatives of the managing authority and the body implementing a joint funding instrument. Programme contribution to joint funding RDI instrument may cover one specific joint funding call or several joint funding calls. Those funding agreements shall include all the elements set out in Annex x.

4. The body implementing joint funding RDI instruments shall keep documentary evidence demonstrating the eligibility of the underlying expenditure.
5. Support from the Funds paid to joint funding RDI instruments shall be managed in line with the principle of sound financial management.
6. Eligible expenditure of a joint funding RDI instrument shall be the total amount of programme contribution set aside for international research projects within the eligibility period.
7. The body implementing the joint funding RDI instrument, shall keep separate accounts or maintain an accounting code for each priority or, for the EMFAF, each specific objective and, where applicable, each category of region for each programme contribution.
8. Resources reserved but unused or paid back before the end of the eligibility period, shall be re-used in the same or other joint funded research, development and innovation calls for final recipients.

4.0 OTHER RESOURCES AND CONTRIBUTIONS

To achieve impact and meet the declared objectives, the Partnership relies also on the mobilisation of research infrastructures as means to support the activities within its thematic intervention areas (in 2024 the intervention areas are 1-Digital Twins of the Ocean, 2-Blue Economy Sectors, 3-Managing Sea-Uses, 4- Blue Bioresources, and 5- Resilient Coastal Communities and Businesses), further strengthening the European Research Area and reinforcing the European ocean observing system. In line with this, beside the launch of joint transnational calls for proposals, the Partnership is mandated to implement additional activities, including by mobilizing contributions different from in cash, to ensure reaching the strategic objectives of the Partnership. The implementation of actions outside competitive calls will require specific technical advice and relevant capacity to foster long-term utilisation and integration of the national implementation dimensions.

In response, the Partnership carried out an analysis on concrete options in terms of availability and in-kind involvement of infrastructures and other existing structured initiatives. Deliverable 8.3 (an output of Task 8.3 – “Options and methodologies to deploy in kind contribution and other linked activities”) – provides recommendations on how to deploy this contribution, with a specific focus on the alignment of (i) thematic annual programming (TAP), (ii) monitoring programmes and (iii) shared use of Research Infrastructures.

With reference to the SBEP, MS and AC need to plan now the strategy for releasing the EU contribution of the second instalment, presently set at 60 M€ and corresponding to about 30% of the total budget. It should be considered that according to the initial estimate by the Partnership Members, the overall in-kind investment is of about the 36% of the entire budget (considering the MS/AC contribution without the EC Top-up). Thus, such contribution has the potential of further leveraging and needs to be sustained in the medium-to-long term.

Further downstream, Task 8.4 will drive the process of organizing the participation to actions not implemented through traditional competitive R&I calls. This will be implemented through a mapping/scouting process of available resources and research infrastructures that will call for interest to contribute these to the SBEP Portfolio. The implementation is likely to vary depending on the nature of the activities, e.g., harmonising national monitoring efforts at sea. Relying on the methodology developed under the current Task 8.2, Task 8.4 will support the deployment of the contribution of Research Performing Organisations, where leveraging their resources and infrastructures, could substantially input to the objectives of the Partnership and the IAs, for example: collection and open access to relevant blue economy data; emerging/new methods, technologies and approaches that are identified as game changers, including beneficial harmonisation of operational protocols; more effective use of monitoring data by quadruple helix stakeholders; development of knowledge and innovation hubs, research infrastructures/platforms for Transnational Access.

4.1 Next steps

Supporting the members of the Partnership Consortium to benefit from an optimal synergy of financial resources for (co)funded research projects is a continuous effort, this task will remain committed to providing dedicated support to implement synergies with other funding programs/strategies for R&I projects during the programming period 2021-2027, aiming to maximize the scientific, economic, and societal impact of the Partnership. This includes continuing, in the 2nd cycle of the Partnership which will start in September 2024, to offer guidelines/recommendations for MS and AC to optimize their administrative and management procedures related to relevant EU and national instruments.

Expanding the work laid by the current Deliverable 8.2, Deliverable 8.5 will further provide and update models/guidelines for optimizing research funding across Europe. Information will be collected, harmonized, and integrated into an interactive, user-friendly digital report/dashboard (Figure 5), serving as a key resource for competitive calls under WP3. This dashboard will enable users to filter information by MS, funding mechanism, and other

pertinent categories. This dynamic living document will also accommodate subsequent updates as developments unfold, facilitating timely dissemination of information.

The WP8 task team will also continue to organise capacity-building actions (workshops, tutorials, and guidelines) accessible to all interested parties from Partnership MS and AC. This effort will synergize with WP5, and all deliverables will be publicly available. It will also directly contribute to WP3 (T3.4), addressing potential synergy with administrative regions within MS and AC to promote their direct involvement in Partnership activities.

Figure 5. Prototype of interactive digital dashboard for displaying up-to-date information on synergies of (financial) resources pertinent to the Partnership.

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